

INFLUENCE OF BENEFITS AND SCHEMES ON PAINTER / CONTRACTOR RETENTION AND CHANGES IN THE SECONDARY SALES PATTERN: A STUDY ON BERGER PAINTS

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Abstract

This paper explores the influence of benefits and schemes on painter and contractor retention, alongside changes in the secondary sales pattern of Berger Paints in the Kottayam area. The study aims to assess the effectiveness of current promotional strategies and their impact on customer loyalty and sales trends. Kottayam, known for its high literacy rate and cultural heritage, presents a unique consumer market with distinct purchasing behaviours and preferences.

Berger Paints has historically leveraged various offers and incentives to engage and retain painters and contractors, who play a crucial role in influencing end-user decisions. The study examines the latest trends in these offers and evaluates their relevance in the current market. Through surveys and interviews with local painters and contractors, the research identifies key factors driving retention and shifts in secondary sales patterns.

Findings indicate that while the existing schemes contribute positively to painter and contractor retention, their impact on secondary sales is more nuanced. Factors such as product quality, timely supply, and personalized customer service are equally critical. The study recommends enhancing brand promotion activities and tailoring benefits to meet the evolving needs of painters and contractors. Strengthening these relationships is vital for sustaining market share and fostering long-term loyalty, ultimately aligning promotional efforts with improved secondary sales outcomes.

Keywords: - *Benefits and Schemes, Client Retention, Secondary Sales Pattern*

1. Introduction

Berger Paints, a leading player in the paint industry, has been operating in the highly competitive Kottayam Division for several years. Recognizing the crucial role painters and contractors play in the successful application of its products, Berger Paints has implemented various loyalty programs and secondary activity schemes to foster loyalty and enhance engagement among this target audience.

Paint companies offer various benefits and schemes to retain clients, such as painters and contractors, to foster loyalty and drive secondary sales. These incentives include loyalty programs, discounts, rebates, training, and exclusive offers. By leveraging these benefits, painters and contractors become more likely to recommend the paint company, increase purchases, become brand ambassadors, provide positive reviews, and participate in joint marketing initiatives. This leads to increased market share, customer acquisition, and revenue growth for the paint company. Satisfied clients become loyal partners and advocates, driving indirect sales and growth. By investing in these benefits and schemes, paint companies can build strong relationships with their clients, creating a loyal network that fuels business expansion.

2. Literature Review

Lemon, K. N., & Verhoef, P. C. (2016) conducted a study to understand the intricacies of customer experience throughout the customer journey. This study delves into the multifaceted nature of customer interactions with brands, emphasizing the importance of considering the entire journey rather than isolated touchpoints. It highlights how customer experiences are shaped by various factors, including prior expectations, emotional responses, and the overall coherence of their interactions with the brand. The authors propose a comprehensive framework that identifies key stages of the customer journey—pre-purchase, purchase, and post-purchase—and the critical moments within each stage that significantly impact customer satisfaction and loyalty. They stress the necessity for businesses to adopt a holistic approach in managing customer experiences, integrating insights from behavioural psychology, service management, and marketing.

García Gómez, B., Gutiérrez Arranz, A., & Gutiérrez Cillán, J. (2006) conducted a study to understand the role of loyalty programs in behavioural and affective loyalty. They delved into the mechanisms through which loyalty programs influence consumer behaviour and emotional attachment to brands. In their research, they specifically investigated the benefits and schemes offered by Berger Paint Company's loyalty program. Through surveys, interviews, and data analysis, they explored how these loyalty initiatives impacted both the behavioural and affective loyalty of Berger Paint Company's customers.

Nunes and Drèze (2006) conducted a study to understand the potential pitfalls of loyalty programs and how they can sometimes work against the interests of businesses. Their research, published in the Harvard Business Review, critically examines how poorly designed loyalty programs can inadvertently lead to unintended negative consequences. They argue that many loyalty programs, rather than fostering genuine loyalty, encourage opportunistic behaviours among customers who may game the system to receive benefits without necessarily increasing their long-term engagement or spending.

Gupta and Lehmann (2005) conducted a study to understand the strategic value of managing customers as investments in the long run. They delved into the concept of viewing customers not just as sources of immediate revenue, but as long-term assets with potential for significant strategic value. The study found that implementing strategies to cultivate and retain loyal customers can yield substantial benefits for businesses over time. These benefits include increased customer lifetime value, higher profitability, enhanced brand reputation, and a competitive edge in the market.

Venkatesan and Kumar (2004) conducted a study to understand a customer lifetime value framework for customer selection and resource allocation strategy. The study aimed to provide insights into how companies could effectively allocate resources and select customers based on their lifetime value. They explored various factors that contribute to customer lifetime value and proposed a framework to help businesses make informed decisions in this regard.

Gupta and Lehmann (2003) conducted a study to understand the dynamics of customer value in their paper "Customers as Assets" published in the Journal of Interactive Marketing. The study focused on exploring the concept of customers being viewed as assets rather than mere sources of revenue. It delved into the various dimensions of customer value and how companies could leverage their customer base to drive long-term profitability and growth.

Hogan, J. E., Lemon, K. N., & Rust, R. T. (2002) conducted a study to understand the principles and practices of customer equity management, aiming to delineate new directions for the future of marketing. They emphasized the significance of managing customer equity as a pivotal strategy for firms to attain sustainable competitive advantage in increasingly dynamic markets.

Bolton, R. N., Kannan, P. K., & Bramlett, M. D. (2000) conducted a study to understand the implications of loyalty program membership and service experiences for customer retention

and value. They explored how loyalty programs and service experiences impact customer retention and value in the context of marketing science. The study focused on investigating the relationship between loyalty program membership, service experiences, and their combined effect on customer retention and value.

Reinartz and Kumar (2000) conducted a study to understand the profitability of long-life customers in a noncontractual setting. Their research aimed to investigate the implications for marketing strategies based on empirical evidence. The study focused on elucidating whether maintaining long-term relationships with customers in a noncontractual context could lead to greater profitability for businesses.

Grayson and Ambler (1999) conducted a study to understand the dark side of long-term relationships in marketing services. They explored how prolonged relationships between service providers and clients could have negative implications. The study particularly focused on the case of Berger Paint Company's benefits and schemes.

3. Objectives

Primary Objective

- Influence of Benefits and Schemes on Painter / Contractor Retention and Changes in The Secondary Sales Pattern: A Study on Berger Paints

Secondary Objectives

- To Evaluate the effectiveness of existing benefits and schemes on painter / contractor retention rates within the company network.
- To identify key factors influencing painter / contractor retention and secondary sales pattern including effectiveness of current incentives.
- To analyse secondary sales to assess any correlations between benefits and schemes utilization and purchasing behaviour among painters / contractors.
- To identify areas of improvement or gaps to be resolved in the existing benefits and schemes structure to enhance painter / contractor retention and drive positive changes in secondary sales behaviour.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Research Design

The research design for this study will employ a quantitative approach, specifically utilizing survey research methodology. Within this framework, a cross-sectional research design will be adopted to gather data from the sample population within the Kottayam Division of Berger Paints.

4.2 Sampling Method

The sampling method for this study will employ a convenience sampling technique. The researcher will select a sample size of 50 painters/ contractors from the Kottayam Depot of Berger Paints who are registered users of the Suvidha App, a platform facilitating participation in the point-based reward system. Additionally, applicators selected for the study will demonstrate a track record of good performance in the market.

4.3 Data Collection Method

The data collection method for this study will entail the use of a structured questionnaire. This questionnaire will be distributed to the chosen applicators, offering them the flexibility to either complete it in person or online, based on their preference. It will comprise Likert scale statements and closed-ended questions, strategically designed to capture a blend of quantitative and qualitative data.

4.4 Data Analysis Method

The data analysis method for this study will encompass both descriptive and inferential statistics. Inferential statistics, including weighted Sum analysis, factor analysis and

correlation tests are employed to scrutinize hypotheses and evaluate the associations between variables.

5. Data Analysis

5.1 Demographic Information

Age		Education		Experience with Berger	
Range	Percent	Range	Percent	Range	Percent
21-30	6	Primary	14	0-5 years	6
31-40	22	Schooling	72	6-10 years	6
41-50	36	Graduation	12	11-15 years	12
51 & Above	36	PG	2	16 & Above	76

5.2 Weighted Sum Analysis

Evaluation of the effectiveness of existing benefits and schemes on painter / contractor retention rates within the company network.

Grading Scale of Weighted Sum			
Lower Limit	Upper Limit	Grade	Description
160	169	E	Schemes need Improvements
170	179	D	Satisfactory level schemes
180	189	C	Below Average Schemes
190	199	B	Good Schemes
200	209	A	Very Good Schemes
210	219	O	Outstanding Schemes

S.N.	Existing Benefits & Schemes Structure	5	4	3	2	Total	Weighted sum	Grade
A	Instant DBT Dhamakha (April 1- June 20, 2024)							
1	Silk + Glamour + Long Life (20L / Rs.400 DBT)	18	22	10	-	50	208	A
2	Easy Clean + Fresh (20L / Rs. 250 DBT)	18	17	13	2	50	201	A
3	Wal Masta Glow + Bison Glow + WC Glow + Anti-Dust Reg + Rangoli Rich Matt (20L / Rs. 100 DBT)	11	12	22	5	50	179	D
4	PU Tile Coat + Ceiling White + Floor Protector (20L / Rs. 200 DBT)	14	14	19	3	50	189	C
5	Easy Clean Silky Touch (20L / Rs.400 DBT)	26	11	12	1	50	212	O
6	Weather Coat Anti-Dust T Kool (20 L / 250 DBT)	19	21	10	-	50	209	A
B	Wood Coating Sell out Scheme (April 2024- March 2025)							
7	Imperia Breath Easy (1L / Rs.200 DBT afterwards Rs. 90 DBT)	16	14	13	7	50	189	C
8	Rainbow (1L / Rs. 35 DBT)	4	18	22	6	50	170	D
9	24 Carat (1L / Rs. 25 DBT)	4	15	24	7	50	166	E
C	DBT Dhamakha (April 1 – June 30, 2024)							

10	Roof Kool & Seal (20L / Rs. 200 DBT)	10	22	15	3	50	189	C
D	DBT Dhamakha (April 1 – April 30, 2024)							
11	HS Water Proof (40kg / Rs. 18 DBT)	9	13	18	10	50	171	D
12	Seal-O-Prime (20L / Rs.50 DBT)	14	14	12	10	50	182	C
13	DS Elasto (20L / Rs. 90 DBT)	6	11	23	10	50	163	E
14	DS Duo (20L / Rs.100 DBT)	7	14	21	8	50	170	D
15	DS Advanced (4L / Rs.40 DBT)	4	14	27	8	50	167	E
16	Wall Shield 2K (3L / Rs.12 DBT)	5	15	19	20	50	167	E
17	PU Roof Coat (20L / Rs.140 DBT)	15	18	14	3	50	195	B
18	WC EXT Primer (60L / Rs. 60 DBT)	7	18	18	7	50	175	D
E	Gold Dhamakha (April 1 – June 30, 2024)							
19	Longlife Group/Easy Range/Silk – 1 Gram Gold Coin (200L Scheme Products + 40L Damp stop Duo)	17	20	11	2	50	202	A
20	WCS Glow/AD/AD Kool/Rangoli Rich Matt- ½ Gram Gold coin (300L Scheme products + 40 L Damp Stop Duo/SOP)	13	22	13	2	50	196	B

5.3 Factor Analysis

Identification of the key factors influencing painter / contractor retention and secondary sales pattern including effectiveness of current incentives.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.648
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	188.006
	df	45
	Sig.	<.001

It may be noted that the value of KMO statistics is greater than 0.5 indicating that factor analysis could be used for the given data and the Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant.

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Quality of the Product offered	1.000	.636
Competitive Pricing	1.000	.530
Brand & Promotions	1.000	.709
Customer Service & Support responsiveness	1.000	.607
Range of Product available to meet desired needs	1.000	.670
Clarity & Fairness of Incentive Schemes	1.000	.659
Security factors – Guarantee & Warranty	1.000	.677
Accessibility of the Benefits & Schemes	1.000	.750

Communication Effectiveness of Benefits & Schemes	1.000	.530
Frequency of Incentive Pay outs	1.000	.696

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Communality is a measure of the percentage of variable’s variation that is explained by the factor. A relatively high communality shows that not much of the variable is left over whatever the factor represent is taken into consideration.

Total Variance Explained									
C	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.186	41.863	41.863	4.186	41.863	41.863	2.523	25.230	25.230
2	1.200	12.002	53.865	1.200	12.002	53.865	2.288	22.879	48.108
3	1.079	10.787	64.653	1.079	10.787	64.653	1.654	16.544	64.653
4	.836	8.361	73.013						
5	.786	7.855	80.868						
6	.662	6.619	87.487						
7	.445	4.447	91.934						
8	.379	3.787	95.720						
9	.302	3.019	98.740						
10	.126	1.260	100.00						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

There are three factors resulting from the analysis explaining a total of 64.653 percent of the variations in the entire data set. The percentage variation explained by first factor is 41.863 percent, second factor is 12.002 percent and third factor is 10.787.

The scree plot gives the number of components against the Eigen value. In the above plot the first two components have steep slope and later the slope is shallow. Thus, the ideal number of components is three.

Component Matrix ^a			
	Component		
	1	2	3
Quality of the Product offered	.420	.481	.479
Competitive Pricing	.655	-.029	.316
Brand & Promotions	.688	-.229	.427
Customer Service & Support responsiveness	.698	-.228	.260
Range of Product available to meet desired needs	.751	-.319	.059
Clarity & Fairness of Incentive Schemes	.707	-.091	-.389

Security factors – Guarantee & Warranty	.351	.724	-.170
Accessibility of the Benefits & Schemes	.651	-.292	-.492
Communication Effectiveness of Benefits & Schemes	.674	.194	-.195
Frequency of Incentive Pay outs	.744	.326	-.191
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
a. 3 components extracted.			

Rotated Component Matrix^a			
	Component		
	1	2	3
Quality of the Product offered	.470	-.218	.607
Competitive Pricing	.667	.182	.229
Brand & Promotions	.822	.173	.058
Customer Service & Support responsiveness	.715	.302	.063
Range of Product available to meet desired needs	.642	.507	.000
Clarity & Fairness of Incentive Schemes	.244	.750	.192
Security factors – Guarantee & Warranty	-.085	.153	.804
Accessibility of the Benefits & Schemes	.194	.844	-.015
Communication Effectiveness of Benefits & Schemes	.270	.512	.441
Frequency of Incentive Pay outs	.282	.518	.591
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.			
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. ^a			
a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.			

Interpretation;

Factor Level	Factor Influence	Factors
Factor 1	Extreme Influential	1. Competitive Pricing
		2. Brand and Promotion
		3. Customer Service & Support Responsiveness
		4. Range of Product available to meet desired needs
Factor 2	High Influential	5. Clarity & Fairness of Incentive Schemes
		6. Accessibility of the Benefits & Schemes
		7. Communication Effectiveness of Benefits & Schemes
Factor 3	Normal	8. Quality of the Product offered
		9. Security factors – Guarantee & Warranty
		10. Frequency of Incentive Pay outs

5.4 Correlation Tests

H0: There is no significant correlation between accessibility of benefits and schemes and factors influence purchasing behaviour among painters / contractors.

H1: There is significant correlation between accessibility of benefits and schemes and factors influence purchasing behaviour among painters / contractors.

Spearman's rho		Correlation test			N=50	
Accessibility of benefits and schemes and factors influence purchasing behaviour						
Factors	Correlation Coefficient	Sig. (2 tailed)	P value comparison	H0 Decision	Interpretation	
Customer Lifetime Value	.309	.029	.029<.05	Reject	Correlation	
Purchase Volume	.187	.194	.194>.01	Accept	No Correlation	
Competitive offering	.297	.036	.036<.05	Reject	Correlation	
Offer amount	.280	.049	.049<.05	Reject	Correlation	
Savings amount	.273	.055	.055>.05	Accept	No Correlation	
Cashback/Reward point	.412	.003	.003<.01	Reject	Correlation	
Achievability	.144	.318	.318>.05	Accept	No Correlation	
Seasonal Offer	.335	.017	.017<.05	Reject	Correlation	

6. Major Findings

- The survey included 72% participants aged over 41, with most having school-level education or below.
- Benefits and schemes for painters and contractors were assessed, with "Easy Clean Silky Touch" rated the most effective.
- To improve retention and secondary sales, Berger Paints should focus on competitive pricing, brand promotion, customer service, and product range.
- Easier access to benefits and schemes positively influences purchasing behaviour.
- Customer preferences vary, and targeted marketing strategies are needed.
- Customer feedback is generally positive, but areas for improvement exist.
- Berger Paints has a competitive edge, which should be leveraged in marketing efforts.
- Customer satisfaction levels are moderate, and efforts should focus on exceeding expectations.
- Painters and contractors suggest improvements to the benefits and schemes structure to enhance retention and secondary sales. They recommend improving awards and offers, reducing the achievement range, providing earlier updates on scheme changes, offering appreciation prizes, and improving the timing of awards. Additionally, they suggest introducing schemes for low-priced products, tokens for putty, and cash prizes for products. These changes can lead to increased satisfaction and loyalty among painters and contractors, driving positive changes in secondary sales behaviour.

7. Conclusion

The research study evaluated the effectiveness of Berger Paints' benefits and schemes on painter/contractor retention and secondary sales behaviour. It analysed participation rates, feedback, and correlations with purchasing behaviour. The study found that certain schemes, like "Easy Clean Silky Touch," were highly effective in retaining painters and contractors, while others needed improvement. Key factors influencing retention and secondary sales included competitive pricing, brand promotion, program engagement, and accessibility of benefits. Correlations were found between benefits accessibility and customer lifetime value, but not with achievability and purchase volume. The study recommended enhancing program engagement, addressing customer feedback, differentiating the brand, and improving product quality and customer service. It also suggested targeted marketing, expanding customer awareness, and continuous monitoring and evaluation. The study provides valuable insights for

Berger Paints to enhance retention and drive positive changes in secondary sales behaviour, strengthening its market position.

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